

IoRT ROS 2 Applications: Evaluating Zenoh and VPN for Robotic Networking in the Edge-Cloud Continuum

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Abstract—Applications in the Internet of Robotic Things (IoRT) add an additional layer of complexity over traditional robotics, namely, networking and communication with the edge and the cloud. The field of cloud robotics has already revolutionized robotic systems, among others, by offloading computationally intensive tasks to the cloud. However, existing approaches are not necessarily suitable for real-time communication and distributed computing, and are not natively supported by widespread robotic middlewares such as ROS 2. Traditional Virtual Private Networks (VPNs) have been widely adopted for secure communication, but often introduce complexity in the setup and latency that can hinder real-time performance. Zenoh, an emerging data-centric networking framework, offers an alternative with low-latency, efficient data dissemination optimized for edge-to-cloud scenarios. Zenoh also integrates seamlessly with ROS 2, enabling lower overhead communication. This paper presents a comparative study of VPN and Zenoh in edge-cloud robotics, focusing mainly on communication latency, data throughput, and fault tolerance within a real-world robotic use case. Through experimental analysis, we highlight the strengths and limitations of both approaches and provide insight into their suitability for distributed robotic applications. The findings contribute to understanding the trade-offs between security, latency, and scalability in networking solutions for the IoRT.

Index Terms—IoRT; Cloud Robotics; ROS 2; Edge-Cloud; SAR

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of cloud computing with robotics, known as cloud robotics, has become a groundbreaking approach in the field of robotics [1]. By leveraging the computational power, storage capabilities, and ubiquitous accessibility of cloud services, robots can handle complex tasks, access vast datasets, and collaborate more effectively [2]. This approach shifts the computational burden from individual robots to distributed cloud systems and enhances capabilities of perception, planning, and decision making, enabling more advanced functions that exceed the limitations of onboard resources alone. Cloud robotics facilitates distributed robot systems, supports scalability, and real-time data sharing among heterogeneous platforms. With ongoing advancements in networking and computing technologies, such as 5G and edge computing, the potential of cloud robotics to revolutionize industries such as manufacturing, healthcare, transportation, and services becomes increasingly significant. The wider field of deploying applications across edge and cloud with a focus on robotic systems is also known as the Internet of Robotic Things (IoRT) [3]. A typical IoRT application stack is illustrated in

Fig. 1: Conceptual illustration of relevant technologies and the typical stack of an IoRT application. On the cloud side, applications typically rely on existing cloud providers (e.g., AWS, Google Cloud, Azure, or private cloud servers), while applications are often containerized using Docker and Kubernetes. Applications can rely on widely used robotic frameworks such as ROS, ROS 2 or NVIDIA Omniverse, or leverage existing tools for remote operations (e.g., RoboLaunch) or fleet management (e.g., OpenRMF). At the edge, applications can be deployed on robotic platforms themselves (ROS, ROS 2), but also include visualization (e.g., Foxglove, rerun), teleoperation (e.g., Formant) or data analytics software that requires real-time communication with both the robots and/or the cloud backend.

Fig. 1, with a selected number of typical technologies and tools for the edge, the cloud and communication middleware layers.

A critical component of cloud robotic systems and wider applications in the IoRT, is the communication framework that facilitates seamless data exchange between robots and cloud systems. Communication reliability, latency, and bandwidth efficiency are key factors determining the overall performance and usability of cloud robotics applications [4]. Reliable and efficient communication is essential to ensure timely data exchange, low-latency responses, and seamless operation across distributed systems. The field has seen remarkable progress in networking technologies, ranging from traditional methods such as Virtual Private Networks (VPNs) to modern data-centric solutions such as Zenoh [5]. Each networking approach

comes with its own set of strengths and challenges, particularly when applied to robotics scenarios where latency, bandwidth, and security are critical [6].

Despite growing interest and development in cloud robotics, there is still a need for a comprehensive review focusing on the specific networking solutions and implementations used in cloud robotics, especially in terms of integration with the Robot Operating System (ROS) and ROS 2 ecosystems [7]. Existing surveys and reviews focus on cloud robotics from broader perspectives, covering theoretical frameworks, general architectures, or specific use cases. However, they often lack an in-depth technical analysis of the current tools, frameworks, and networking solutions available for ROS-based cloud robotics.

This paper addresses this gap by presenting a detailed comparison of VPN and Zenoh as networking solutions for cloud robotics. Specifically, we evaluate their performance in terms of communication latency and data throughput within a real-world use case. Through this analysis, we aim to provide actionable insights into the suitable networking frameworks for various cloud robotics scenarios, highlighting the strengths and limitations of each approach.

Contributions of this paper:

- 1) A systematic comparison of VPN and Zenoh in a cloud robotic application, evaluating key networking performance metrics.
- 2) Experimental analysis of Zenoh over different transport protocols (TCP, QUIC, TLS) to assess their impact on latency and reliability.
- 3) Implementation and validation of networking solutions in real-world use case of NEPHELE project, demonstrating practical IoRT applications.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews the state-of-the-art networking solutions for cloud robotics, with a focus on integration into ROS and ROS 2. Section III introduces our use case. Section IV discusses the system assumptions and architectures. Section V explains the detailed environment setup and experimental methodology. Section VI concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

Recent research on cloud robotics has emphasized the use of cloud-based infrastructures to augment robotic capabilities, enabling advanced computational tasks, large-scale data storage, and seamless collaboration in distributed environments. For example, Waibel et al. introduced the RoboEarth architecture [8], a cloud-based platform where robots share knowledge, including object models, environment maps, and task strategies, to enhance robot adaptability and collaboration. Robofleet [9], as presented by Sikand et al. provided an open-source communication and management system for robot fleets. The FogROS2 series provides further insights into the evolution of cloud robotics networking. FogROS2 [10] initially focused on optimizing cloud computation for single robots, emphasizing latency reduction and performance improvement via VPN integration. Its later iterations, such as

FogROS2-SGC [11] extended to secure, globally connected ROS 2 communications, while FogROS2-LS [12] introduced dynamic routing and location-independent services. FogROS2-FT[13] emphasized fault tolerance and cost-effectiveness by leveraging multi-cloud platforms and spot virtual machines to ensure continuous cloud service. In addition to VPNs, other approaches include the use of blockchain technology, such as the Hyperledger Fabric framework, to establish a communication and decision-making system in distributed robotic systems [14], [15]. Some of these works are also focused on additional functionality, such as auditability of teleoperation or proof of location services [16].

From the perspective of the cloud infrastructure and distributed computing beyond communication, Zhang et al. explored KubeROS [17], which integrates Kubernetes with ROS for container orchestration, enhancing the deployment and management of ROS nodes in large-scale environments. These works collectively highlight the diverse approaches in framework and networking for cloud robotics. Notably, while VPNs have been widely used as a networking solution in these systems, there has been little exploration of Zenoh approach. This lack of implementation motivates a detailed comparison between the current VPN-based solutions and Zenoh, focusing on their performance, QoS, and fault tolerance in distributed robotics environments.

Zenoh [18] has emerged as a promising networking solution optimized for modern distributed systems and cloud robotics due to its low-latency, lightweight communication protocol. Zenoh combines location-independent communication with a data-centric approach, enabling efficient data sharing across distributed systems. Zenoh natively supports publish/subscribe patterns, distributed queries, and resource discovery, enabling low-latency and high-throughput communication that is particularly suitable for edge-to-cloud scenarios. Recent evaluations of Zenoh [6] highlight its unparalleled performance in networking scenarios, outperforming MQTT, Kafka, and even DDS in specific metrics. Zenoh's ability to provide dynamic adaptability and optimization techniques makes it ideal for real-time robotics applications in resource-constrained environments.

VPNs are widely used to provide secure, encrypted communication over public and private networks. By establishing secure tunnels, VPNs ensure data integrity and confidentiality, which are essential for scenarios involving sensitive data exchange between robots and the cloud [10]. However, VPNs are not without limitations. One of the primary challenges is the introduction of additional latency, which can significantly impact the performance of real-time robotic applications. VPNs encrypt and route data through remote servers, which can increase data transmission latency [19]. Moreover, setting up ad-hoc VPNs for distributed robotic applications introduces complexity for application developers.

While VPNs and Zenoh have been individually studied, there is a lack of direct comparisons evaluating their performance under identical conditions in distributed robotics. This paper aims to address this gap by systematically comparing

VPN and Zenoh, focusing on their performance in real-world distributed robotic systems.

III. USE CASE: NEPHELE

NEPHELE [20] is a research project focusing on networking technologies for hyper-distributed applications. It addresses challenges like dynamic resource allocation, low-latency communication, and scalability to enable real-time applications in complex environments. One of NEPHELE's key use cases involves a cloud-based robotic system designed for post-disaster response, where interoperability between heterogeneous IoT devices, such as ground robots, drones, and environmental sensors, is crucial for situational awareness and decision-making [21]. This system is deployed using Kubernetes and integrates the Web of Things (WoT) framework to operate remote navigation, real-time mapping, and autonomous perception in unknown environments. Inspired by this use case, our experiment evaluates different networking approaches, VPN and Zenoh, in the context of cloud robotics, analyzing their impact on communication latency, reliability, and data throughput when applied to distributed robotic operations.

IV. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Cloud robotics leverages distributed computing to enhance robotic capabilities, requiring efficient and secure communication between robots and cloud infrastructure. Two possible solutions, analyzed and presented in this paper, for establishing this communication are VPNs and Zenoh as illustrated in Fig. 2. In this section, we introduce their architectural differences, operational mechanisms, and their impacts on robotic applications.

A. VPN-based architecture

A VPN creates a secure, encrypted tunnel between two or more devices over the Internet. This ensures that data transmitted between the involved devices is encrypted, protecting it from eavesdropping or tampering. Figure 2a illustrates a VPN-based setup using WireGuard VPN for secure connectivity between a Kubernetes (k8s) cluster and a robotic system running ROS 2.

The main components of this architecture include:

- 1) Kubernetes Cluster: The edge-hosted environment manages the deployment and orchestration of ROS 2 Docker containers and nodes.
- 2) ROS 2 Container: This container runs ROS 2 nodes, which communicate with each other using the ROS 2 middleware.
- 3) WireGuard VPN: This VPN establishes a secure tunnel, enabling communication between the edge and the robot.
- 4) Cyclone DDS: ROS 2 nodes use the Cyclone DDS middleware for data distribution, relying on multicast communication over the VPN tunnel.
- 5) Robot System (Ubuntu 16.04): The robot integrates a ROS bridge for backward compatibility and support (older) ROS driver. It also runs ROS 2 nodes in a Docker container that communicates with the cloud through the VPN tunnel.

B. Zenoh-based architecture

Figure 2b illustrates a Zenoh-based system that replaces VPN-based communication with Zenoh routing and bridging mechanisms.

The key components of this architecture are:

- 1) Kubernetes Cluster: Similar to the VPN architecture, the edge-based environment manages the deployment of ROS 2 Docker containers and a Zenoh router.
- 2) DDS-Zenoh Bridge: This component bridges ROS 2 (using DDS) with Zenoh, enabling interoperability between the two protocols.
- 3) Zenoh Router: The router facilitates efficient data exchange between the edge and robots by forwarding messages based on a publish-subscribe model, optimizing data routing and reducing latency.
- 4) Robot System (Ubuntu 16.04): The robot hosts ROS 2 nodes connected through the DDS-Zenoh bridge, ensuring low-latency, direct communication with the edge.

A key advantage of Zenoh is its ability to operate over different transport protocols, each impacting network performance. In this study, we compare VPN-based communication with three Zenoh transport options - Transmission Control Protocol (TCP), Transport Layer Security (TLS), and QUIC (Quick UDP Internet Connections), to evaluate their suitability for cloud robotics networking. **TCP-based Zenoh** ensures reliable, ordered communication and is widely compatible with existing networking infrastructure. However, its connection-oriented mechanism may introduce higher overhead and latency, particularly in lossy networks (e.g., WiFi). **TLS-based Zenoh** builds on TCP by adding encryption, ensuring secure end-to-end communication. While it provides strong confidentiality and integrity, the additional cryptographic overhead can increase latency, making it less ideal for real-time applications. **QUIC-based Zenoh**, in contrast, leverages a UDP-based transport protocol with built-in encryption and multiplexing, offering lower latency and improved performance over unreliable networks. Its ability to reduce handshake delays and packet retransmission overhead makes it particularly interesting for real-time and dynamic robotic applications.

The evaluation focuses on latency, throughput and efficiency, providing insights into how different networking architectures influence performances in real-world robotic applications.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this Section we report on the performance evaluation for the proposed approaches for our system. We used a Summit-XI robot equipped, among others, with a front depth camera and running Nav2 [22] for the scope of this evaluation. Indeed, we choose to focus our analysis only on a subset of the ROS topics for having a clearer understanding of the impact the architecture approach and transport protocols have, constrained by the networking conditions. The access to the Internet is guaranteed by a 802.11b WiFi access to the campus network with a maximum WiFi bandwidth available on the robot of about 6 MB/s.

Fig. 2: Illustration of the two architectures compared in this paper.

A. Methodology

A custom ROS 2 C++ subscriber node is written to log the necessary data from the ROS topics. For having a fair comparison between the two considered approaches only two topics are exchanged via the transport protocols. The two topics are the stereo depth topic from a RGB-D camera and the local costmap data from the Nav2 navigation algorithm. The subscriber node runs simultaneously for 5 minutes on the Docker container started on the robot and in a container running on the Kubernetes cluster. Both containers run Ubuntu 22.04 with ROS 2 Humble. The ROS node subscribes to the topic data and logs the following data: (i) published timestamp; (ii) received timestamp; (iii) payload size. The clocks are synchronized using NTP.

The QoS of the topics subscribed is kept the same as published by their respective ROS nodes. The QoS of the stereo depth data is reliable with a history depth of 10 and volatile durability. The QoS of the costmap data is reliable with a history depth of 1 and transient local durability. After the script finishes it outputs the median and mean latency in seconds.

B. Experimental Results

We focus on the following four test cases, and measure the corresponding latency and data throughput values for the following topics: (i) 4 Hz, (ii) 8 Hz, (iii) 10 Hz, and (iv) 13 Hz for the camera depth, with costmap at a constant 1.7 Hz. The throttling is performed by the *topic tools* package in ROS 2. The selected test cases give a good overview of the impact of the topic publishing rate on performance, while analyzing two topics that either send a large amount of data (i.e., camera depth topic) and a low amount of data (i.e., costmap topic). While the packet data sent is fixed to 0.61 MB, the depth camera topic will send many more messages than the costmap topic, which depending on the transport protocol will induce retransmissions. Note that the latency values we will report next, refer to the topic messages and not on the single data packets sent as regulated by the transport protocol being used. Therefore, higher latency values will be observed as more messages are sent per single topic publishing.

In Test 1, with effective camera depth data frequency of 4.3 Hz, we see in Fig.3 that all the transfer protocols receive 100% of the data sent. In terms of latency, see Fig.4, the VPN has the lowest median latency of about 0.47 secs. The median latencies of the Zenoh protocol (TCP, QUIC and TLS) are also

Fig. 3: Stereo depth data received at the cloud server (percentage), for different data rates. These results give a qualitative idea on reliability of the data transport.

Fig. 4: Latency distribution of stereo depth data around 4 Hz

quite similar to about 0.52 secs.

In Test 2, with effective camera depth data frequency of 7.6 Hz, we obtain similar results, as we can see in Fig.3 and Fig.5. All the transfer protocols receive 100% of the data. In terms of the median latency, the VPN has still the lowest latency of 0.47 secs and the remaining 3 Zenoh protocols of 0.52 secs.

In Test 3 with effective camera depth frequency of 10 Hz, we notice that all the protocols have higher latency w.r.t. the previous 2 tests and differentiations among the tested solutions appear.

Although the VPN achieves the lowest median latency at 1.2 seconds, its latency variance is significantly higher (ranging from 0.4 to 2.6 seconds), see Fig.6, indicating instability in

Fig. 5: Latency distribution of stereo depth data around 8 Hz

Fig. 6: Latency distribution of stereo depth data at 10 Hz

Fig. 7: Latency distribution of stereo depth data at 13 Hz

data delivery. This shows that the VPN has a high standard deviation (0.41 secs) of the latency values.

In contrast, Zenoh protocols maintain more consistent latency values. This result is important as in a robotic application like high-speed autonomous drones where constant frequency of sensor data or high speed odometry is required, the VPN cannot be trusted for providing data at constant frequencies. On the other hand, the Zenoh protocols provide higher but more reliable latency measurements. The QUIC protocol provides the least median latency of about 1.4 secs, as expected. The TCP and TLS are a little bit higher at about 1.7 secs of median latency.

Noteworthy, in terms of the throughput the VPN performed very poorly as it received only 15% of the transmitted data. On the other hand, the Zenoh protocols receive about 95% of the transmitted data.

In Test 4 effective camera depth data frequency is 12.8 Hz. Here the WiFi bandwidth is already exceeded and forms the bottleneck for the scenario. This means that many errors retransmissions of data messages are expected influencing negatively throughput and latency values. In this test we observe from Fig.7, that the QUIC protocol has the lowest median latency of about 1.3 secs. The VPN has a bit higher median latency of about 1.4 secs. The TCP and the TLS have even higher median latencies of about 1.7 secs.

In terms of the throughput the Zenoh protocols receive about 75% of the data sent due to the WiFi bottleneck but the VPN almost fails to provide any usable data for the ROS topic.

As seen in Table I the costmap data has much lower latency

TABLE I: Median Latency (secs) Comparison

	Stereo Depth				Costmap			
	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Test 4	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Test 4
VPN	0.47	0.47	1.18	1.45	0.01	0.05	0.24	0.29
TCP	0.52	0.53	1.71	1.71	0.02	0.08	0.72	0.73
Quic	0.53	0.53	1.37	1.32	0.03	0.07	0.30	0.31
TLS	0.52	0.53	1.66	1.72	0.02	0.08	0.74	0.75

for all the tests than the stereo depth data. This is due to the low packet size of the costmap data which is 3600 bytes per sec compared to the 0.61 MB per sec for the stereo depth data.

TABLE II: Data Received in Percent Comparison

	Stereo Depth				Costmap			
	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Test 4	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Test 4
VPN	100.00	100.00	15.22	1.03	100.00	100.00	20.71	4.39
TCP	99.95	99.94	94.68	73.32	100.00	99.57	80.81	76.66
Quic	99.99	100.00	95.75	77.20	100.00	99.40	89.22	85.73
TLS	100.00	99.96	96.93	73.57	100.00	98.22	85.58	75.73

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presents a detailed comparison between VPN and Zenoh as networking solutions for cloud robotics. Specifically, we have looked at their integration with DDS, the default data communication middleware in ROS 2 applications, and deployment in edge-to-cloud communication. Through an experimental evaluation, we analyzed their performance in terms of latency, throughput, and reliability in a real-world robotic use case. The results indicate that while VPNs provide secure communication, they introduce higher latency and reduced throughput, making them less suitable for real-time distributed robotic applications. In contrast, Zenoh demonstrates superior performance in latency-sensitive scenarios, particularly with the QUIC transport protocol, which offers lower median latency and higher data throughput compared to VPNs.

Our findings suggest that Zenoh is a preferable alternative for communication in edge-to-cloud robotic applications. In particular, it is most suitable for robots requiring low latency data exchange and efficient resource utilization.

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